

BROMINATION OF COMPOUNDS CONTAINING TWO AROMATIC NUCLEI.
PART XVI. BROMINATION OF SOME ARYLAMIDES OF 2-HYDROXY-
3-METHYLBENZOIC ACID (*o*-CRESOTIC ACID)

BY MRS. V. R. PATAKOOT AND G. V. JADHAV

Bromination of anilide, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidides, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilides, *o*- and *p*-anisidides, *p*-phenetidide and β -naphthylamide of *o*-cresotic acid has been carried out in presence of acetic acid as well as with liquid bromine. The constitution of the bromo derivatives has been proved by hydrolysing them and identifying the acidic and basic components

Present work is the continuation of that of Jadhav and Nerlekar (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1951, 20, Pt. III, 97) taken up with a view to ascertaining the effect of substituting the negative $-\text{NO}_2$ group by $-\text{CH}_3$ group towards bromination. In the present work it is observed that the molecule is rendered more reactive, as by brominating the compounds as before in hot solution only, bromine is found to enter both the nuclei simultaneously, and hence, no pure bromo derivative can be isolated when the reactants are used in the proportion 1:1, excepting in the case of *p*-toluidide, and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroanilides. With more bromine solution dibromo derivatives were obtained in all cases excepting in the case of nitroanilides. Liquid bromine furnished higher bromo derivatives excepting in the case of *o*- and *p*-toluidides

The constitutions of all the bromo derivatives have been arrived at by hydrolysing them and identifying the acidic and basic components.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromination in Acetic Acid Medium.—The arylamide (1 g.) was dissolved in boiling acetic acid and 50% solution of bromine in acetic acid was added to it excepting in the case of β -naphthylamide where the addition was done at 70° to 80°. Bromo product began to separate as the reaction mixture cooled down. The products are described in Table I. The yield of the bromo derivatives varied from 1.5 to 1.8 g.

Bromination with Liquid Bromine.—The arylamide (2 g.) was gradually added to liquid bromine (3 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature, when the solid went into solution. The solution was then diluted with water and the solid obtained was triturated with sodium bisulphite solution to remove excess of bromine. It was then crystallised from a suitable solvent. The compounds are described in Table II.

Hydrolysis.—The bromo derivatives excepting those of *o*- and *p*-anisidides, *p*-phenetidide and β -naphthylamide were hydrolysed by boiling with 10% solution of NaOH (100 c.c. for 1 g.) for several hours, as mentioned against the respective compound in the table. The mixture was then diluted and extracted with ether. The base obtained from ether was identified by mixed melting point with genuine specimens excepting in the case of bromo-*p*-toluidine and bromo-*p*-anisidine which were identified through their acetyl derivatives.

TABLE I

[B represents 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-benz-, B-5-B represents 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-bromo-benz-].

Amide used.	Acetic acid.	Bromine soln.	Bromo derivative.	Cryst. shape.	M.P.	Formula.	% Bromine Found.	% Bromine Calc.	Period of heating for hydrolysis.
B-anilide	30 c.c.	6.0 c.c.	B-5-B-4'-bromo-anilide *	White needles	162-63°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBr ₂	41.7	41.6	8 hr.
B-o-toluidide	15	5.2	B-5-B-4'-bromo-o-toluidide †	" plates	154-55°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	40.4	40.1	7
B-m-toluidide	40	5.2	B-5-B-4'-bromo-m-toluidide *	" needles	162-63°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	40.2	40.1	6
B-p-toluidide	30	2.5	B-5-B-p-toluidide *	" "	162-63°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	25.2	25.0	12
B-β-toluidide	30	5.4	B-5-B-2'-bromo-p-toluidide †	Pinkish needles	204-5°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	40.2	40.1	14
B-o-nitroanilide	40	3	B-5-B-o-nitroanilide *	Yellow needles	184-85°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Br	23.1	22.8	8
B-m-nitroanilide	40	3	B-5-B-m-nitroanilide *	White plates	210-11°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Br	22.6	22.8	6
B-p-nitroanilide	60	3	B-5-B-p-nitroanilide *	Greenish plates	265-66°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Br	22.7	22.8	8
B-o-anisidide	30	5	B-5-B-5'-bromo-o-anisidide †	White needles	145-46°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	38.5	38.6	7
B-p-anisidide	30	5	B-5-B-3'-bromo-p-anisidide †	Do	185-86°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	38.4	38.6	6
B-p-phenetidide	20	5	B-5-B-3'-bromo-p-phenetidide †	Do	184-85°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	37.2	37.3	7
B-β-naphthylamide	25	5	B-5-B-1'-β-naphthylamide †	Yellow needles	145-46°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₂	36.6	36.8	6

* Crystallised from alcohol.

† dil. alcohol.

‡ acetic acid.

TABLE II

[B represents 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-benz- and B-5-B represents 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-bromo-benz-].

Amide used.	Bromo derivative.	Cryst. shape.	M. P.	Formula.	% Bromine Found.	% Bromine Calc.	Period of heating for hydrolysis.
B-anilide	B-5-B-2'-4'-dibromoanilide	White plates	197-98°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NBr ₃	51.5	51.7	12 hr.
B-m-toluidide	B-5-B-4'-6'-dibromotoluidide	" needles	183-84°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ NBr ₃	50.2	50.2	16
B-p-toluidide	B-5-B-2'-bromo-p-toluidide	Pinkish needles	204°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₃	40.2	40.0	14
B-o-nitroanilide	B-5-B-4'-bromo-2'-nitroanilide	Yellow needles	168-69°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Br ₂	37.4	37.2	10
B-m-nitroanilide	B-5-B-6'-bromo-3'-nitroanilide	White needles	205.6°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Br ₂	37.3	37.2	8
B-p-nitroanilide	B-5-B-2'-bromo-4'-nitroanilide	Brown needles	240-41°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ Br ₂	37.1	37.2	10
B-o-anisidide	B-5-B-5'-6'-dibromo-o-anisidide	Light red needles	149-50°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr ₃	48.7	48.6	8
B-p-anisidide	B-5-B-2'-5'-dibromo-p-anisidide	White needles	215-16°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr ₃	48.5	48.6	7
B-p-phenetidide	B-5-B-2'-5'-dibromo-p-phenetidide	Do	245-46°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr ₃	47.4	47.2	7
B-β-naphthylamide	B-5-B-1'; 3'-6'-tribromo-β-naphthylamide	Yellow needles	163-64°	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBr ₄	53.7	53.9	8

All bromo derivatives in Table II were crystallised from acetic acid except that of *o*-nitroanilide which, was crystallised from alcohol and that of *o*-anisidide which was crystallised from dilute acetic acid. Yields of bromo derivatives were between 1.7 to 2 g.

The acid obtained from the alkaline solution on acidification was always found to be 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-bromobenzoic acid.

In the case of the bromo derivatives of *o*- and *p*-anisidides, *p*-phenetidide and β -naphthylamide, hydrolysis was carried out by heating on a boiling water-bath with 80% H_2SO_4 (30 to 50 c.c. was used for 2 g.) for several hours. The reaction mixture was then diluted and the solid obtained was filtered. The filtrate on neutralisation afforded the base which was extracted with ether. The solid obtained from ether was identified by mixed melting point with genuine specimens.

The solid, insoluble in acidic solution, was then extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution and the acid was precipitated from it on acidification. It was identified as 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-5-bromobenzoic acid.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY.

Received August 22, 1955.